

The Role of the Teacher Taken by ChatGPT

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: ChatGPT, Drill, Facilitator, Teacher

Received : 3 December

Revised : 18 December

Accepted: 21 January

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ABSTRACT

The utilization of ChatGPT in Society 5.0 can span various fields, such as education, health, business, and public services. The aim of this research is to determine the extent to which ChatGPT can be used to replace the role of a teacher. The research methodology employed is a comparative experiment. The first population consists of a group of students taught by uninspiring lecturers, using a drill-based learning model without reflective and conclusions steps. Meanwhile, the second population comprises a group of students learning by interacting with ChatGPT. The first sample consists of 14 individuals with normally distributed data. The second sample consists of 13 individuals with similarly normally distributed data. Both samples are homogeneous. The results of this study suggest that there is no significant difference in the learning outcomes of students taught by teachers using a drill-based learning model without reflective and conclusions steps, compared to students who only interacted with ChatGPT

INTRODUCTION

The era of Society 5.0 represents the latest development in the evolution of society influenced by technology, particularly artificial intelligence. This era is characterized by the deepening integration of technology into everyday life, not merely as tools but also as solutions to solve complex social problems (Manik, 2022). One notable aspect of Society 5.0 is the active involvement of humans in the decision-making process, where technology supports human roles in achieving better solutions.

In this context, the presence of ChatGPT, as a representation of advanced artificial intelligence, makes a significant contribution to realizing the vision of Society 5.0. ChatGPT is a language model capable of understanding and generating human-like text, facilitating more effective communication between humans and machines. With its ability to comprehend context, respond to questions, and generate high-quality text, ChatGPT becomes a valuable tool in facilitating information exchange and problem-solving in the era of Society 5.0. The utilization of ChatGPT in Society 5.0 can span various fields such as education, health, business, and public services (Manik et al., 2023). In education, for instance, ChatGPT can serve as an intelligent learning assistant, aiding students and teachers in information exchange and problem-solving. In the healthcare sector, ChatGPT can be used to provide quickly accessible and accurate medical information to the public. Thus, the integration of ChatGPT in Society 5.0 opens new opportunities to harness artificial intelligence to enhance the quality of life and improve efficiency across various sectors.

The use of ChatGPT in mathematics education opens up new opportunities to enhance the interaction between students and technology in the educational process. ChatGPT can serve as an intelligent learning assistant that helps students understand mathematical concepts, providing personalized explanations and responsive answers to students' questions. With its ability to grasp context and present information in familiar language, ChatGPT can make learning mathematics more easily understandable and engaging.

Students can pose questions to ChatGPT to seek assistance in solving math problems, explaining challenging concepts, or obtaining additional information related to specific topics. Additionally, ChatGPT can present example problems and solutions, aiding students in mastering calculation skills, algebra, geometry, and other mathematical concepts. This approach can personalize the students' learning experience, allowing them to learn at their own pace and focus attention on areas requiring additional understanding.

The use of ChatGPT in mathematics education can also assist teachers by providing additional support in creating more varied and comprehensible learning materials. Teachers can leverage this technology to develop more interactive teaching materials, motivate students, and provide faster feedback on their learning progress. Thus, the integration of ChatGPT in mathematics education can create a more dynamic learning environment, supporting students in developing their mathematical skills more effectively.

The question of whether ChatGPT can replace the role of a teacher is a crucial debate in the evolution of educational technology. While ChatGPT can provide information quickly and accurately, the success of learning is also closely tied to the personal interaction between teachers and students, encompassing motivation, a profound understanding of students' learning needs, and the ability to guide critical thinking processes. In this context, a comprehensive study is needed to assess the extent to which ChatGPT can be an effective tool in supporting the role of a teacher without completely replacing it. The research problem formulation in this study is to what extent ChatGPT can be used to replace the role of a teacher.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Teachers as facilitators in learning play a crucial role in creating an interactive and student-centered learning environment (Reeve, 2006). In this role, teachers serve not only as a source of knowledge but also as mediators who assist students in understanding and developing their own capabilities. This approach emphasizes active student participation, where teachers act as a bridge between the learning material and the real-life experiences of students.

As facilitators, teachers design challenging learning situations that motivate students to think critically. They employ various teaching methods and strategies, such as group discussions, collaborative projects, and independent exploration, to stimulate the creativity and problem-solving skills of students. Teachers also recognize the diversity in students' learning styles and strive to create learning experiences that are relevant and engaging for all students.

Moreover, teachers as facilitators help students develop social skills, collaborative abilities, and a sense of responsibility for their own learning. By providing appropriate support, teachers encourage students to become independent learners capable of continuous lifelong learning. This approach aligns with the evolution of modern education, emphasizing the development of 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration.

In this context, teachers not only serve as information conveyors but also as mentors who inspire and support the full potential development of each student. By being facilitators in learning, teachers create a positive atmosphere in the classroom, motivating students to explore knowledge and helping them develop the skills necessary for success in life.

Mathematics teachers, as facilitators in learning problem-solving, have a significant responsibility in developing students' problem-solving skills and critical thinking. In the context of mathematics learning, facilitators play a role in providing challenges that motivate students to face various types of mathematical problems (Borko et al, 2014). They are not just providers of correct answers but more of guides who help students understand the mathematical concepts underlying each problem.

As facilitators, mathematics teachers create learning situations that allow students to formulate questions, outline solution steps, and test problem-solving strategies. By employing this approach, teachers assist students in developing logical, analytical, and creative thinking skills. They provide support to students

in understanding the mathematical processes, reinforcing conceptual understanding, and encouraging the application of knowledge in different contexts.

Furthermore, mathematics teachers as facilitators promote collaborative learning, where students work together to solve complex mathematical problems. This collaboration not only hones students' social skills but also provides space for sharing various problem-solving approaches. Facilitators guide discussions, stimulate the exchange of ideas, and provide constructive feedback.

With this approach, mathematics teachers create a challenging yet supportive learning environment, helping students overcome fears of mathematics and sparking their interest in the subject. As facilitators, mathematics teachers play a role in shaping students' analytical thinking and laying a strong foundation for mathematical abilities that they will apply in their daily lives and future careers.

Mathematics teachers have a crucial role in guiding students facing difficulties or feeling uncertain about solving mathematical problems found in textbooks. In addressing such situations, the teacher's approach may include steps that support students' understanding and development.

Firstly, mathematics teachers can invite students to talk about their understanding of the problem. By listening to students' thoughts, teachers can identify the points of difficulty they are experiencing and provide additional explanations accordingly. Additionally, teachers can motivate students to formulate further questions or try to develop solution steps.

Next, teachers can use guiding questioning methods to lead students toward the correct answers. The questions posed by the teacher should stimulate students' critical thinking, help them see the connections between concepts, and guide them through the steps toward the right solution. This approach allows students to build their understanding rather than relying solely on the answers provided by the teacher.

Mathematics teachers often assume a more traditional role rather than that of a learning facilitator (Lessani et al, 2017). They tend to prioritize an instructive teaching approach, with steps such as directly explaining the material to students. This process involves verbally delivering mathematical information and often focuses on fundamental concepts. In an effort to ensure understanding, teachers often choose to demonstrate the steps for solving problems and provide concrete examples.

In addition, mathematics teachers often emphasize practice through solving problems as an integral part of learning. They may instruct students to work on a series of exercises as homework or in class. This approach aims to sharpen calculation skills and apply previously taught mathematical concepts. While these steps can help build a foundation of mathematical knowledge, there is a question of whether this approach optimally stimulates students' critical thinking and creativity.

The outlined learning steps above bear resemblance to the drill learning model long known in the context of education. Essentially, the drill learning model involves several stages, including teaching the material, working on example problems or activities step by step, assigning students to solve problems or complete activities progressively, and finally, a stage of reflection and conclusion (Manik, 2020).

The first stage of the drill model, teaching the material, reflects an instructive approach where the teacher plays a central role in delivering information to students. The teacher systematically explains the material for students to understand fundamental concepts. After that, the second stage involves working on example problems or activities step by step, where students can apply their understanding through concrete exercises. The third stage involves assigning students to solve problems or complete activities progressively, emphasizing independent practice and applying concepts in different contexts.

It is important to remember that the drill learning model can provide a strong foundation in understanding the material, but attention should be paid to ensure that learning is not limited to mechanical repetition. Therefore, the reflection and conclusion stages are essential to ensure deep understanding. Through reflection, students can evaluate their learning process, identify weaknesses, and gauge their understanding of the taught mathematical concepts. Conclusions drawn from this reflection can serve as a basis for the development of more complex understanding and the application of mathematical concepts in broader contexts.

Facing the pressure to cover a considerable amount of curriculum, mathematics teachers often feel compelled to focus on information delivery and mechanical exercises without giving adequate attention to the reflection and conclusion stages in the drill learning model. In this situation, there is a likelihood that critical aspects of students' understanding of mathematical concepts may be overlooked.

The reflection and conclusion stages in the drill model play a significant role in ensuring that students not only master the material mechanically but also have a deeper understanding. Unfortunately, time constraints often lead mathematics teachers to sacrifice these stages in pursuit of covering a broader range of material. Yet, through reflection, students can evaluate how they understand and solve problems, identify common mistakes, and develop more effective strategies.

Without the steps of reflection and conclusion, mathematics learning can become routine and limited to achieving mechanical end results. Students may be able to answer questions correctly without truly understanding the underlying concepts. Therefore, it is crucial for mathematics teachers to find the right balance between covering material and providing space for reflection, allowing students to acquire a deeper and sustainable understanding of mathematics. This step will help students develop critical thinking and valuable problem-solving skills in their mathematical development.

Without involving the steps of reflection and conclusion in the drill learning model, there is a significant chance that learning may be limited to mere mechanical achievements. In situations where time constraints often push teachers to focus on teaching and exercises without allowing room for reflection, students' role in replacing this step through questioning ChatGPT becomes an intriguing alternative.

Students asking questions to ChatGPT can stimulate independent critical thinking and reflection. They have the opportunity to delve deeper into mathematical concepts, pose questions arising from their own understanding, and receive in-depth explanations from this language model. This interaction not only helps students solve the problems they face but also gives them control over their own learning process.

By replacing the sometimes less reflective drill learning model, students can leverage technology to gain a more contextual and profound understanding. ChatGPT not only provides answers but also enables students to undergo a systematic thinking process and build mathematical knowledge continuously. Therefore, this approach offers a more dynamic and responsive way to address the individual needs of students in the process of learning mathematics.

Mathematics teachers remain crucial in actively engaging in students' learning. Teachers can utilize direct interaction to provide in-depth feedback, encourage discussions on concepts, and ensure that students have a solid understanding. Teachers of this kind will be able to inspire their students to learn independently and progress. Concurrently, the implementation of technology and online self-directed learning can be a beneficial complement as long as it is wisely integrated to enhance students' mathematics learning experience.

One uninspiring learning model is the drill learning model without reflection and conclusion steps. Mathematics teachers often use the drill learning model without reflection and conclusion steps following the sequence of material in students' textbooks or modules. Teachers frequently ask students about what they don't understand at each step. Based on the students' answers, teachers will explain the concepts that students have not mastered.

From the theoretical discussion above, it is inferred that if a teacher lacks inspiration, the teacher's presence can be replaced by ChatGPT and other online applications. To test this statement in the context of education, teachers will provide modules as a structured source of student learning. Subsequently, teachers will utilize a drill learning model without reflection and conclusion steps, engaging in activities such as responding to students' questions about concepts, providing example problems, and presenting questions found in the modules. Thus, the research hypothesis is formulated as follows: there is no difference in learning outcomes between students taught by uninspiring teachers and students who only inquire with ChatGPT.

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology employed in this study is a comparative experiment. The first population consists of a group of students taught by uninspiring lecturers, while the second population comprises students who learn by asking ChatGPT. Random sampling is conducted to select participants. The students will be instructed to study systematically prepared modules aligned with the existing curriculum. At the end of the learning process, both sample groups will undergo a post-test. The post-test scores will be analyzed as the basis for drawing conclusions with a 90% confidence level.

RESULTS

This research was conducted in the Mathematics Education Study Program at Universitas HKBP Nommensen during the Numerical Methods course in the year 2023. Random sampling was employed, with the first sample consisting of 14 individuals and the second sample comprising 13 individuals. Each student was instructed to study systematically prepared modules in accordance with the curriculum. The research focused on the topic of numerical integration. One meeting before the study, each group was conditioned to the learning situation they would encounter during the research.

The first sample underwent learning taught by an uninspiring lecturer. Students were asked to independently study the distributed modules and could pose questions to the lecturer regarding the concepts, example problems, and questions within the modules. The lecturer would answer the students' questions. This activity was repeated throughout the learning process following a drill learning model. After three sessions, students participated in an exam by working on post-test questions. The post-test scores for students taught by the uninspiring lecturer can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. The Post-Test Scores of Students With Uninspiring Lecturer

No	Value	Frequency
1	1	2
2	2	1
3	3	3
4	4	1
5	5	2
6	6	1
7	7	1
8	8	3
Sum		14

The second sample engaged in learning by asking questions to chatGPT. They studied in a computer laboratory that could access chatGPT online. Students were required to independently study the distributed modules. If they didn't understand the module content, they were only allowed to ask chatGPT for clarification. This process was repeated throughout the learning period. After three sessions, students took an exam by working on the same post-test questions as the first sample group. The post-test scores for students who learned with chatGPT can be found in Table 2.

Table 2. The Post-Test Scores of Students Learning with ChatGPT

No	Value	Frequency
1	2	2
2	3	2
3	4	3
4	5	2
5	6	2
6	8	1
7	10	1
Sum		13

The first sample consists of 14 individuals with an average of 4.92 and a standard deviation of 2.25. The data for the first sample are normally distributed. The second sample comprises 13 individuals with an average of 4.77 and a standard deviation of 2.31. The data for the second sample are also normally distributed. Both samples are homogeneous as the calculated F is 1.06, which is smaller than the F table for α equal to 10%. Since the calculated t is -0.17 within the acceptance region of H_0 , the Null Hypothesis is accepted, indicating: There is no significant difference in the learning outcomes of students taught by a teacher using the drill learning model compared to those who only ask questions to ChatGPT.

DISCUSSION

The drill learning model provides a more structured learning experience but can sometimes feel monotonous and less engaging. Learners may feel restricted in creativity and idea exploration. On the other hand, asking ChatGPT can create a more interactive and engaging learning experience. Dynamic interaction with this model can enhance learner engagement, making learning more enjoyable and challenging.

The drill learning model has several drawbacks compared to asking ChatGPT. The drill learning model tends to produce static answers and is limited to specific contexts. Teachers may respond to questions with contextual understanding that is not deep or does not integrate information from various

sources. In contrast, asking ChatGPT allows for more dynamic and adaptive interactions, as this model is trained on a large amount of data and can respond to questions in a more complex and contextual manner.

A drawback of the drill learning model is the potential fear of learners to ask questions impolitely and repetitively. In contrast, for ChatGPT, learners are free to ask questions in a more informal style, even repeatedly. ChatGPT responds better to variations in language styles as it has engaged in various contexts and communication styles during its training.

The modules provided to learners in this study are highly beneficial to ensure that the teaching materials are well-structured. However, if teachers use the drill learning model, merely answering students' questions about concepts, example problems, and exercises in the module, the results may be less than optimal (Manik, 2020). The outcomes would be much better if teachers teach using the Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) model (Manik, 2020). Teachers are recommended to use HOTS models, including (1) the Discovery/Inquiry Learning model, (2) Problem-Based Learning (PBL) model, (3) Project-Based Learning (PjBL) model with various variations such as Jurisprudential Inquiry, and others (Panjaitan & Manik, 2015).

From the results of this research, the drill learning model without reflection and conclusion steps used by the teacher can be effectively replaced by ChatGPT. Moreover, with ChatGPT, learners do not need to be afraid to repeatedly ask about the teaching materials until they truly understand. ChatGPT can also provide several alternative solutions when requested. Such conveniences will enhance the insights of the learners.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion of this study is that there is no significant difference in the learning outcomes of students taught by teachers using the drill learning model without reflection and conclusion compared to students who only ask questions to ChatGPT. This result is obtained when all students have received a structured module as their learning source. Thus, teachers can be replaced by ChatGPT if they teach using the drill learning model without reflection and conclusion. The recommendation from the findings of this research is that teachers are encouraged to use a more effective model, namely the Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) learning model.

FURTHER STUDY

The next research that can be conducted is to compare learning with ChatGPT with learning using the Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) learning model.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Gratitude is extended to HKBP Nommensen University for funding this research. May the Lord continue to bless this institution for further advancements in the days ahead.

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